

Amine - and Mixed Amine—Tungsten Tricarbonyls

S. C. TRIPATHI,* S. C. SRIVASTAVA, G. PRASAD AND A. K. SHRIMAL

Department of Chemistry, University of Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur (U.P.)

Long time thermal reactions of hexacarbonyl tungsten(0) with butylamine, cyclohexylamine and benzylamine give white fibrous trisubstituted derivatives [W(CO)₃Am₃] (Am=butylamine, cyclohexylamine and benzylamine). Morpholine and piperidine yield only disubstituted products. Mixed amine tungsten tricarbonyls of the type [W(CO)₃B Am] (B=*o*-phenanthroline or 2, 2'-bipyridine) have also been synthesized. The C-O stretching frequencies have been measured and assigned.

IN our earlier communications¹⁻³ we have reported the reactions of several bases with hexacarbonylmolybdenum(0). Here we describe the preparation and characterization of several new amine substituted and mixed ligand tungsten tricarbonyls containing aliphatic, alicyclic and heterocyclic amines. Amine substituted derivatives of tungsten carbonyl are less familiar. Only mono⁴⁻⁷ and in a few cases di^{4, 7} substituted derivatives have been reported. To our knowledge no trisubstituted derivative except diethylenetriaminetricarbonyltungsten(0)⁸ has been prepared by direct reaction of amine with hexacarbonyltungsten(0).

Experimental

Hexacarbonyltungsten(0) (Diamond Alkali Co., U.S.A.) was sublimed before use. All the experiments were performed under dry nitrogen or *in vacuo*. Infrared spectra were measured on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer model 237.

Preparation of tris(butylamine) tricarbonyltungsten(0)

Hexacarbonyltungsten(0) (0.4g) and butylamine (5.0ml) were refluxed in xylene (10ml.) for 18 h in nitrogen atmosphere. The colour of the reaction first changed to light yellow and finally to dark red. A fibrous white residue settled down at the bottom of the flask. When the reaction was over, the white residue was filtered and was washed first with petroleum ether (40°-60°) and then with diethyl ether. The residue was dried *in vacuo*. It was identified to be tris (butylamine)—tricarbonyltungsten(0) (0.334 g ; 61.3 %).

Anal. calcd for C₁₅H₃₃N₃O₃W : C,36.9 ;
H, 6.7 ; N, 8.6
Found : C, 36.1 ; H,6.5 ; N,8.4

It was insoluble in almost all the organic solvents except tetrahydrofuran in which it was sparingly soluble. It did not decompose up to 220°C.

Preparation of tris(cyclohexylamine)tricarbonyltungsten(0)

Hexacarbonyltungsten(0) (0.4 g) and cyclohexylamine (5.0 ml) were refluxed in xylene (10 ml) for 20 h in nitrogen atmosphere. The product was isolated using identical procedure. The fibrous white residue (0.453 g ; 70 %) which was identified to be tris(cyclohexylamine) tricarbonyltungsten(0) decomposed between 193°—199°C without melting.

Anal. calcd for C₂₁H₃₉N₃O₃W : C,44.6 ;
H, 6.9 ; N,7.4
Found : C, 44.9 ; H,6.4 ; N,7.3

It resembled in solubility and stability with its butylamine analogue.

Preparation of tris(benzylamine) tricarbonyltungsten(0)

Hexacarbonyltungsten(0) (0.4 g) and benzylamine (5.0 ml) were refluxed in xylene (10 ml) for 22 h in nitrogen atmosphere. The product was isolated using identical procedure. The fibrous white residue (0.378 g ; 55.0 %) which was identified to be tris (benzylamine) tricarbonyltungsten(0) did not decompose upto 220°C.

Anal. calcd for $C_{24}H_{27}N_3O_3W$: C,48.8 ; H,4.5 ; N,7.1

Found : C,47.2 ; H,4.3 ; N,7.0.

It resembled with its butylamine analogue in physical characteristics.

Preparation of o-phenanthroline(butylamine) tricarbonyltungsten(0)

Hexacarbonyltungsten(0) (0.2 g) and *o*-phenanthroline (0.102 gm) were refluxed in butylamine (5.0 ml) for 3 h. After one hour of reflux needle shaped black crystal appeared in the flask. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature. The excess of amine was decanted out and the black solid was washed several times with benzene (5 ml. portions). The black solid was recrystallised in a mixture (1:1) of nitrogen bubbled methanol and acetone under nitrogen. The compound was identified

to be *o*-phenanthroline(butylamine) tricarbonyltungsten (o) (80%).

Anal. calcd for $C_{19}H_{19}N_3O_3W$: C,43.7 ; H,3.6 ; N,8.0

Found : C,42.9 ; H,3.7 ; N,8.2

It was insoluble in hydrocarbons, light petroleum, sparingly soluble in diethylether and soluble in methanol, acetone and dichloromethane. It decomposed instantaneously when it was dissolved.

Table 1 lists the method of preparation, yield and microanalysis of the other products.

Results and Discussion

In the present investigation we have been able to synthesize three tris(amine)tungsten tricarbonyls namely, tris(butylamine)tricarbonyltungsten(0), tris

TABLE I

Compound and colour	Method and conditions	Yield (%)	Analysis, found (Calcd.) %		
			C	H	N
[W (<i>o</i> -Phen)(CO) ₃ (C ₂ H ₅ N ₂)] Black	Reflux 4 h.	71.6	41.0 (40.1)	3.2 (3.1)	11.1 (11.0)
[W (<i>o</i> -Phen)(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)] Black	Reflux 3 h.	90.1	46.7 (46.0)	3.8 (3.8)	7.9 (7.6)
[W (<i>o</i> -Phen)(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH ₂)] Violet Black	Reflux 4 h.	63.1	50.0 (47.5)	3.0 (3.0)	7.6 (7.5)
[W (<i>o</i> -Phen)(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₁₁ N)] Violet Black	Reflux 3 h.	81.7	45.5 (45.0)	3.6 (3.5)	7.9 (7.8)
[W (<i>o</i> -Phen)(CO) ₃ (C ₄ H ₉ NO)] Violet	Reflux 4½ h.	78.5	43.0 (42.6)	3.3 (3.1)	8.2 (7.8)
[W (2,2'-Bipy)(CO) ₃ (C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂)] Black	Reflux 3 h.	76.2	40.3 (41.0)	4.1 (3.8)	8.5 (8.4)
[W (2,2'-Bipy)(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)] Black	Reflux 3 h.	89.1	43.4 (43.5)	3.9 (4.0)	8.0 (8.0)
[W (2,2'-Bipy)(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH ₂)] Violet Black	Reflux 3 h.	69.1	45.0 (45.1)	3.2 (3.2)	7.8 (7.9)
[W (2,2'-Bipy)(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₁₁ N)] Violet Black	Reflux 3 h.	74.7	42.2 (42.4)	3.7 (3.7)	8.4 (8.2)
[W (2,2'-Bipy)(CO) ₃ (C ₄ H ₉ NO)] Violet	Reflux 5 h.	66.5	39.9 (39.9)	3.4 (3.3)	8.1 (8.2)

(cyclohexylamine) tricarbonyltungsten(0) and tris (benzylamine) tricarbonyltungsten(0) by refluxing hexacarbonyltungsten(0) in corresponding amines using xylene as solvent in nitrogen atmosphere for a long time (20 h.). In mild conditions only mono- and disubstituted derivatives are obtained. The preparation and properties of mono- and disubstituted derivatives have been described elsewhere.^{9, 10} Further substitutions beyond the trisubstituted stage could not be achieved even by applying more drastic conditions, i.e. by increasing the reaction time and employing high boiling solvents. Piperidine and morpholine yielded the products only up to disubstituted stage in identical conditions. It has been observed that aliphatic and alicyclic amines are more reactive towards hexacarbonyltungsten(0) than the heterocyclic amines. The trisubstituted products so obtained were almost insoluble in most of the polar and nonpolar solvents. They are very air sensitive even in solid state. They decompose instantaneously when they are dissolved. Since these complexes decompose rapidly in solutions, their infrared spectra have been measured in mull phase.

The mixed ligand derivatives [W(CO)₃B Am] were prepared by refluxing under nitrogen equimolar mixtures of hexacarbonyltungsten(0) and *o*-phenanthroline or 2, 2'-bipyridine in amines like butylamine, ethylenediamine, cyclohexylamine, benzylamine, piperidine or morpholine. With triethylamine, quinoline, or acridine mixed complexes of the type [W(CO)₃B Am] could not be isolated. All the mixed derivatives are black crystalline solids, insoluble in hydrocarbons and light petroleum; they are sparingly soluble in diethyl ether. They dissolve in methanol, acetone and dichloromethane with a violet colour and decompose rapidly in solutions to yield ash like residue.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectra of the [W(CO)₃Am₃] complexes indicated that they were *cis*-derivatives, having C_{3v} symmetry. The two CO bands (table II) both of strong intensity are assigned for A₁ and E modes respectively. These bands are comparable with the bands of their molybdenum analogues. A band present at 1587 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of all the three complexes may be attributed to the N-H deformation band.

The molecular geometry of the mixed *cis*-[W(CO)₃ B Am] derivatives is consistent with C_s symmetry ; three carbonyl bands due to 2A' + A''

TABLE II—CO STRETCHING FREQUENCIES FOR *CIS*-[W (CO)₃Am₃] COMPLEXES

Complex	Frequency	Mode
[W(CO) ₃ (C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂) ₃]	1874 s	A ₁
	1718 s	E
[W(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂) ₃]	1874 s	A ₁
	1718 s	E
[W(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH ₂) ₃]	1887 s	A ₁
	1724 s	E

s=Strong.

modes are expected. Except the two cases where only one broad CO band is observed due to A' + A'' modes, all the complexes exhibit three strong CO bands in their infrared spectra (Table III) in agreement

TABLE III—CO STRETCHING FREQUENCIES FOR [W(CO)₃B Am] COMPLEXES

Complex	Frequency	Mode
[W (<i>o</i> -Phen)(CO) ₃ (C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂)]	1885 s	A'
	1760 s	A'
	1742 s	A''
[W (<i>o</i> -Phen)(CO) ₃ (C ₂ H ₅ N ₂)]	1885 s	A'
	1760 s	A'
	1742 s	A''
[W (<i>o</i> -Phen)(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)]	1885 s	A'
	1754 br	A' + A''
[W (<i>o</i> -Phen)(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH ₂)]	1885 s	A'
	1765 s	A'
	1745 s	A''
[W (<i>o</i> -Phen) (CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₁₁ N)]	1885 s	A'
	1765 s	A'
	1742 s	A''
[W (<i>o</i> -Phen)(CO) ₃ (C ₄ H ₉ NO)]	1885 s	A'
	1765 s	A'
	1745 s	A''
[W (2,2'-Bipy)(CO) ₃ (C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂)]	1888 s	A'
	1760 s	A'
	1738 s	A''
[W (2,2'-Bipy)(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)]	1885 s	A'
	1758 br	A' + A''
[W (2,2'-Bipy)(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH ₂)]	1885 s	A'
	1760 s	A'
	1742 s	A''
[W (2,2'-Bipy)(CO) ₃ (C ₆ H ₁₁ N)]	1888 s	A
	1765 s	A'
	1742 s	A''
[W (2,2'-Bipy)(CO) ₃ (C ₄ H ₉ NO)]	1888 s	A'
	1765 s	A'
	1742 s	A''

s=Strong, br=Broad

with the above requirement. One of the CO bands lay between 1885-1888 cm^{-1} , while the other two between 1760-65 and 1738-1745 cm^{-1} . The splitting of E mode (of C_{3v} symmetry) into $A' + A''$ is small. This is an indication of near equivalence of the bonding properties of B and Am ligands which we have concluded by evaluating the ratio of two types of *cis* CO-CO interaction force constants.¹¹ Further the position of *o*-phenanthroline and 2, 2'-bipyridine in the spectrochemical series is very close to that of other amines which is also an indication of near equivalence in their bonding properties. It is important that, for corresponding molybdenum analogues the E mode was unsplit and a slightly broad single band was recorded (C_{3v} symmetry was inferred for the local symmetry of the carbonyl groups undisturbed from the hexacarbonylmolybdenum octahedral). The difference may be encountered in the light of the greater size of tungsten compared to molybdenum. Greater size of the metal atom may contribute greater to the distortion of the molecule from C_{3v} symmetry. This lowering of symmetry may lift the degeneracy of E mode causing the splitting of E mode into A' and A'' in C_8 symmetry.

Acknowledgement

We thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi (INDIA) for a Research grant to (A.K.S.). A gift of hexacarbonyltungsten(0) from

the Diamond Alkali Co. (U.S.A.) is also gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. S. C. TRIPATHI and S. C. SRIVASTAVA., *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1970, **23**, 193.
2. S. C. TRIPATHI and S. C. SRIVASTAVA., *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1970, **25**, 193.
3. S. C. TRIPATHI, S. C. SRIVASTAVA and R. D. PANDEY., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 457.
4. G. W. A. FOWLES and D.K. JENKINS., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 257.
5. W. STROHMEIER, J. F. GUTTENBERGER., H. BLUMENTHAL and G. ALBERT., *Chem. Ber.*, 1966, **99**, 3419.
6. F. A. COTTON and C. S. KRAIHNZEL., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 533.
7. W. STROHMEIER, K. GERLACH and D. V. HOBE., *Ber.*, 1961, **94**, 164.
8. E. W. ABEL, M. A. BENNETT and G. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 2323.
9. S. C. TRIPATHI, S. C. SRIVASTAVA and G. PRASAD., *Proc. Xth. Int. Conf. Coordin. Chem.*, Japan, 1967, p. 38.
10. S. C. TRIPATHI, S. C. SRIVASTAVA and G. PRASAD., *Proc. XIth Int. Conf. Coordin. Chem.*, Israel, 1968, p. 447.
11. L. W. HOUK and G. R. DOBSON., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 2119.